

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Exploring MHD Effect on Eyring-Powell Nanofluid Through Porous Media Under The Influence of Slips

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Abstract

Objectives: This study aims to investigate the first and second order slip effects, thermal and solutal convective conditions of the magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) flow behaviour of Eyring-Powell nanofluid through a porous stretching sheet, taking into account the presence of Casson fluid particles.

Method: The primary governing equations are a collection of nonlinear partial differential equations that have been similarly transformed into sets of nonlinear ordinary differentials of nanofluid motion, energy, and concentration along with the boundary conditions by using similarity transformations. These equations are numerically solved by using an implicit finite element method. **Findings:** This study reveals the influence of various factors on velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles and it is observed that the presence of velocity diminishes with the increasing values of magnetic field parameter, Casson fluid parameter and second order slip parameter while increases the velocity with Eyring Powell parameter and first order slip parameter. Thermophoresis parameter (Nt) shows the same effect on both temperature and concentration profiles whereas Brownian motion (Nb) parameter demonstrates opposite effect with the increment values in Nt, Nb. Tabular data is used to offer detailed information on skin friction, heat rate, and mass transfer coefficients. **Novelty:** The uniqueness of this study lies in its comprehensive analysis of the combined effects of MHD, slip, and Casson fluid behaviour on the flow of Eyring-Powell nanofluid through porous medium and heat transfer characteristics. The findings provide valuable insights into the complex interactions between these factors also this study will pave the way for future finite element method software implementation and offering new perspectives and potential applications in various engineering and industrial processes involving fluid flow and heat transfer phenomena.

Keywords: Powell-Eyring fluid; Casson fluid; Magnetic field; Porous medium; First and second order slips; Stretching sheet; Finite element method

1 Introduction

The need for increased heat transfer rates in industrial manufacturing processes is widely recognized. To meet these requirements we have a shortage of traditional heat transfer techniques. As a result scientists concentrated their scientific endeavours on developing methods to enhance heat transfer abilities. The argument behind the fluid additives is to enhance the thermal performance of ordinary liquids like oil, water and ethylene-glycol mixture. Numerous studies have highlighted the efficacy of solid-liquid mixtures in enhancing heat transfer. However, concerns such as clogging, abrasion, and additional pressure loss have been raised, rendering such mixtures unsuitable for improving thermal performance.

Nanoparticles play a crucial role in enhancing the physical properties like electronics cooling, transformer cooling, and heat exchanger of conventional liquids. Moreover, the integration of magneto nanofluids has shown remarkable potential in medicine, engineering, and physics, with applications ranging from MHD generators and pumps to boundary layer control. The concept of nanofluids is suggested by Choi⁽¹⁾, and he confirmed by experimentally that the thermal performance of carrier liquids could be dramatically enhanced by the addition of tiny solid or metallic particles. Further the mechanism of movement of nanoparticles in ordinary base fluids is explored by Buongiorno⁽²⁾ considering the factors such as nanoparticle size, inertia, particle agglomeration, and Brownian motion. In the present study we employ the Buongiorno model to investigate the convective heat transfer characteristics in nanofluids. Contrary to previous homogeneous-flow models, which often under predicted heat transfer coefficients, Buongiorno's model accounts for particle migration within the fluid, offering a more accurate representation of heat transfer phenomena. Because of more applications of boundary layer flows induced by stretchable surfaces in various engineering and industrial processes, including cooling of metallic sheets, polymer extrusion, and crystal growth and it is observed that the stretching of surface is not linear inevitably in all the situation. In this context recent research has further explored the boundary layer flow behaviour of nanofluids induced by stretching surfaces.

Due to much attention of non-Newtonian materials and its applications in industrial and engineering so far Navier–Stokes expression is used to characterize the flows of non-Newtonian materials and which is not sufficient to explain the characteristics of all the non-Newtonian materials. Therefore, various types of non-Newtonian relations are given in the literature. Under such consideration the Powell–Eyring fluid model is one of the fluid model. This model has important characteristics because its constitutive expressions can be deduced from kinetic theory of gases instead of empirical expression as in power law model. Moreover, it can correctly reduce to Newtonian liquid flow case for high and low shear rates whereas power law model depicts an infinite effective viscosity for low shear rate.

The assessment of the intensity of movement in the progression of Powell-Eyring liquid across a plate is the primary focus of the text that was indicated before. This evaluation takes into consideration the drop in velocity and temperature that occurs when the fluid parameter is raised. In contrast to this, the Eyring-Powell liquid model, which is mentioned in sources⁽³⁾⁽⁴⁾, proposes that depending on a practical relationship is the best way to understand the connection. The creation of entropy in MHD Eyring-Powell nanofluids on strained surfaces was described by Bhatti et al.⁽⁵⁾. This was accomplished using Chebyshev spectral collocation and iterative linearization respectively. Based on the findings of this research, it seems that the profile that generates entropy is being more impacted by all physical elements. Numerous models are used to illustrate various elements of non-Newtonian fluids. This is because of the complexity of these fluids' properties. The Powell-Eyring fluid model is recognized as one of the fluid models that are being discussed. According to Khan et al.⁽⁶⁾, its flow is crucial because, in contrast to the power law model, it can be derived from a kinetic theory of gases rather than a practical connection. This is the reason why its flow is so important. The researchers Abdul Halin and Mohd Noor⁽⁷⁾ carried out an investigation on a sheet that is stretched vertically and includes Powell-Eyring fluid that is infused with nanoparticles. A combination of active and passive control of Nano crystals was used in the computation of the solution. Their results suggested that the total heat transfer rates of the non-Newtonian nanofluid were lowered owing to the combined impacts of Brownian motion, thermophoresis, and nanofluid features. In the research that Jamshed and colleagues⁽⁸⁾ conducted, they investigated the formation of entropy and the transmission of heat by the Powell-Eyring fluid as it moved through a material that was not homogeneous and expanded linearly. The transport of heat is decreased by upsurging the Joule heating and magnetic field parameters for both contracting and extending states is noticed in the study of flow of mixed convection for radiative and magnetic hybrid nanofluid in a porous material with Joule heating⁽⁹⁾. The investigation of the two-dimensional flow over a stretched sheet was carried out by Malik et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ using a mix of convection and an MHD Eyring-Powell nanofluid flow experiment. A study based on heat generation and thermal radiation impacts on flow of magnetic Eyring–Powell hybrid nanofluid in a porous medium revealed that the transport nature of heat is decreased by increase of magnetic field and permeability of porous medium. The thermal radiation and heat generation improved, the heat transfer increased⁽¹¹⁾. Exploration of heat variation on MHD Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow with convective boundary condition and Ohmic heating in a porous material is made, the results of increase of permeability, Biot and Eckert numbers improved the temperature profile and slowdown heat transfer process. In addition, convective boundary condition and thermal radiation enhances the friction of the surface⁽¹²⁾. Mohamed R. Eid worked on the Thermal conductivity variation and heat generation

effects on magneto-hybrid nanofluid flow in a porous medium with slip condition. Increase in nanoparticle concentration enhances the heat transfer rate of the hybrid nanofluid in a shrinkable case, the opposite results are noticed in a stretchable state⁽¹³⁾. There are several factors that might potentially influence the creation and pace of cooling of the desired feature. One of these factors is magnetohydrodynamics (MHD). According to the findings of Agrawal and Kaswan⁽¹⁴⁾, an MHD Eyring-Powell nanofluid was investigated. This nanofluid displayed a surface that was greatly expanding and unstable, in addition to entropy formation and heat radiation. Abdelhafez and his team members worked on the effects of yield stress and chemical reaction on magnetic two-phase nanofluid flow in a porous regime with thermal ray. This report elucidates that the transport of heat increased by increase of porous medium permeability, thermal radiation, chemical reaction and magnetic field, Whereas, increase of heat sink/source and yield stress reduce the heat transfer, while the adverse behavior is observed with the transmit of mass for these parameters⁽¹⁵⁾. Several writers⁽¹⁶⁻¹⁹⁾ investigated the flow characteristics of Eyring-Powell fluid flow in the presence of various fields. Recently⁽²⁰⁻²³⁾ many authors such as Nadeem et. al⁽²⁴⁾ investigated the flow of an Eyring Powell Nanofluid in a porous peristaltic channel through a porous medium and Al-Mamun⁽²⁵⁾ studied the numerical simulation of periodic MHD Casson nanofluid flow through porous stretching sheet. Effect of viscous flow on MHD Maxwell nanofluid with Joule heating in a porous medium is studied. The results witnessed in heat transfer enhances with the order of chemical reaction increase. The enhancement in Joule heating, chemical reaction and Biot number rises the mass transfer, whereas in the opposite direction the mass transfer is reduced as the magnetic parameter, permeability and the order of chemical reaction increases⁽²⁶⁾. Also, Suresh Kumar et al.⁽²⁷⁾ carried Numerical analysis of magnetohydrodynamics Casson nanofluid flow with activation energy, Hall current and thermal radiation and Ebba Hindebu Rikitu and team⁽²⁸⁾ studied the Flow Dynamics of Eyring-Powell Nanofluid on Porous Stretching Cylinder under Magnetic. Newly Abbas & Meenakumari^(29,30) researched on MHD dissipative Powell-Eyring fluid flow due to a stretching sheet with convective boundary conditions and slip velocity and MHD 3D flow of Powell Eyring fluid over a bidirectional non-linear stretching surface with temperature dependent conductivity and heat absorption/generation and Flow Dynamics of Eyring-Powell Nanofluid on Porous Stretching Cylinder under Magnetic Field and Viscous Dissipation Effects. Recently, study on two dimensional radiative Casson-Carreau hybrid nanofluid flow through a circular cylinder in a Darcy-Forchheimer porous medium was reported by Ahmed Rashad et. al. In this work, an improvement in heat, thermal radiation, yields enhancement in the velocity profile is noticed⁽³¹⁾. MHD effect on Jeffery hybrid nanofluid flow over a moving porous surface with Yield stress impact revealed in mass transport is upsurged with increase of chemical reaction and heat source. It also witnessed the higher permeability, parameters of yield stress, generation of heat and magnetic field enhance distribution of temperature and slow down the heat transfer⁽³²⁾. Recent report of Ahmed M. Rashad group explored the variation of thermal conductivity and heat on magnetic Maxwell hybrid nanofluid viscous flow in a porous system with higher order chemical react witnessed the heat and mass transfer are decreases by increase of magnetic field, Maxwell parameter, and permeability of porous media. Additionally, enhance in the order of chemical reactions improves the mass transfer. Increase of thermal conductivity and heat source/sink improves mass transfer but decreases the heat transfer⁽³³⁾.

The combined effects of thermophoresis, porous medium, Brownian motion, and the first and second order slip effects of Casson-Powell-Eyring fluid flow, as well as nanoparticles, on magnetohydrodynamic boundary layer flow across a stretched sheet have not received much attention in the literature. In the current study, the Casson-Powell-Eyring nanofluid is compared to magnetic parameter, thermophoresis, porous medium, Brownian motion, first and second order slip flow, and boundary layer flow towards stretched sheet. Using a similarity transformation methodology, the governing partial differential equation of the boundary layer flow region is turned into its corresponding ordinary differential equation, which is then numerically solved using the finite element method. The effects of developing variables on fluid velocity, temperature, concentration, skin friction, rate of heat transfer, and rate of mass transfer coefficients were also explored and shown using graphs and tables. The fundamental goal of this study is to close this gap. The goal of this study is to improve heat transfer in renewable energy and industrial thermal management systems.

2 Methodology

In the current study it is considered steady two-dimensional (2D) flow of an incompressible Powell-Eyring nanofluid over a nonlinear stretchable sheet enclosed by porous medium with the effect of second order slip and convective heat and mass conditions are imposed at the boundary. Casson fluid particles, magnetic field, Brownian motion, thermophoresis, and thermal radiation effects are accounted. The surface of the sheet is heated through the hot fluid having temperature T_f and concentration C_f that give heat and mass transfer coefficients β_1 and λ_1 respectively. The coordinate axes are chosen as the x -along the flow direction and y – axis normal to it as shown in the Figure 1. The plate is stretched along x -axis with a velocity $u_w = ax^n$, where $a > 0$ is stretching parameter. Effects of electric field and Hall current are neglected. Fluid is taken electrically conducted via non-uniform magnetic field $B(x)$ in the y – direction. The magnetic Reynolds number is assumed small and so, the induced magnetic field can be considered to be negligible. Based on the above hypotheses the equations for two-dimensional (2D)

boundary layer flow of Powell–Eyring nanofluid are given as follows^(34,35) and solved by finite element method. The rheological equation for a non-Newtonian fluid is defined as,

$$\tau = \tau_o + \mu\alpha^* \tag{1}$$

Fig 1. Physical Coordinate representation of the Casson- Powell-Eyring nanofluid

Equation (1) can be expanded for Casson fluid as,

$$\tau_{ij} = \begin{cases} 2 \left(\mu_B + \frac{P_y}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \right) e_{ij}, \pi > \pi_C \\ 2 \left(\mu_B + \frac{P_y}{\sqrt{2\pi_C}} \right) e_{ij}, \pi < \pi_C \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Where $\pi = e_{ij}e_{ji}$ with e_{ij} is the $(i, j)^{th}$ component of the fluid deformation rate and $p_y = \frac{\mu_B \sqrt{2\pi}}{\gamma}$ is the yield stress of the Casson fluid.

Continuity Equation:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0, \tag{3}$$

Momentum Equation:

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \left(\nu + \frac{1}{\rho_f \chi C^*} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{2\rho_f \chi C^{*3}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \left(\frac{\sigma B^2(x)}{\rho_f} \right) u - \nu \left(\frac{u}{k_1} \right), \tag{4}$$

Equation of thermal energy:

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \alpha_m \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{(\rho C)_p}{(\rho C)_f} \left\{ D_B \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right\} - \frac{1}{(\rho C)_f} \left(\frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} \right), \tag{5}$$

Equation of species nanoparticle volume concentration:

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = D_B \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2}, \tag{6}$$

The boundary conditions for this flow are⁽³⁴⁾

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u = u_w(x) + u_{slip}, v = 0, -\kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \beta_1 (T_f - T), -D_B \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = \lambda_1 (C_f - C) \text{ at } y = 0 \\ u \rightarrow 0, T \rightarrow T_\infty, C \rightarrow C_\infty \text{ as } y \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{7}$$

The radiative heat flux q_r (using Rosseland approximation) is defined as

$$q_r = -\frac{4\sigma^*}{3K^*} \left(\frac{\partial T^4}{\partial y} \right) \tag{8}$$

We assume that the temperature differences within the flow region, namely, the term T^4 can be represented as linear function of temperature. The best linear approximation of T^4 is obtained by expanding it in a Taylor series about T_∞

$$T^4 = T_\infty^4 + 4T_\infty^3 (T - T_\infty) + 6T_\infty^2 (T - T_\infty)^2 + \dots \tag{9}$$

After neglecting higher-order terms in the above equation beyond the first-degree term in $(T - T_\infty)$, we get

$$T^4 \cong 4T_\infty^3 T - 3T_\infty^4 \tag{10}$$

Thus substituting Equation (10) in Equation (8), we get

$$q_r = -\frac{16T_\infty^3 \sigma^*}{3K^*} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) \tag{11}$$

Using Equation (11), Equation (5) can be written as

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \alpha_m \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{(\rho C)_p}{(\rho C)_f} \left\{ D_B \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right\} + \frac{1}{\rho C_p} \left(\frac{16T_\infty^3 \sigma^*}{3K^*} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right), \tag{12}$$

The governing equations can be reduced to ordinary differential equations, using the following similarity transformation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u = ax^n f'(n), v = -\sqrt{\frac{av(n+1)}{2}} x^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \left\{ f(n) + \left(\frac{n-1}{n+1} \right) n f'(n) \right\}, \\ n = y \sqrt{\frac{a(n+1)}{2v}} x^{\frac{n-1}{2}}, \theta = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_f - T_\infty}, \phi = \frac{C - C_\infty}{C_f - C_\infty} \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{13}$$

Using the similarity transformations Equation (13), the basic governing equations Equation (4), Equation (6), and Equation (12) along with boundary conditions Equation (7) take the following forms:

$$(1 + \beta) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) f'' - \left(\frac{n+1}{2} \right) \beta \lambda f''' f'' + f f'' - \left(\frac{2n}{n+1} \right) (f')^2 - (M + K) f' = 0, \tag{14}$$

$$\left(1 + \frac{4R}{3} \right) \theta'' + Pr f \theta' + Pr Nb \theta' \phi' + Pr Nt \theta'^2 = 0, \tag{15}$$

$$Nb \phi'' + Nb Le Pr f \phi' + Nt \theta'' = 0, \tag{16}$$

the corresponding boundary conditions are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f'(0) = 1 + \vartheta f'(0) + \omega f''(0), f(0) = -\delta(1 - \theta(0)), \theta'(0) = -\varsigma(1 - \theta(0)), \\ f'(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \theta(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \phi(\infty) \rightarrow 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{17}$$

where the involved physical parameters are defined as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \beta = \frac{1}{\mu x C^*}, \lambda = \frac{u_w^3}{2vx C^{*2}}, M = \frac{2\sigma B_o^2}{\rho_f a(n+1)}, K = \frac{v}{\alpha_m}, \varsigma = \frac{\lambda_1}{D_B} \sqrt{\frac{2v}{a(N+1)}}, \\ Nb = \frac{(\rho C)_p D_B (C_f - C_\infty)}{v(\rho C)_f}, Nt = \frac{(\rho C)_p D_T (T_f - T_\infty)}{v(\rho C)_f T_\infty}, Le = \frac{v}{D_B}, R = \frac{4T_\infty^3 \sigma^*}{K^* k}, \\ \delta = \frac{\beta_1}{k} \sqrt{\frac{2v}{a(n+1)}}, Re_x = \frac{u_w x}{v}, \vartheta = A \sqrt{\frac{a(n+1)}{v}}, \omega = \frac{Ba(n+1)}{v}, \gamma = \frac{\mu_B \sqrt{2\pi}}{P_y} \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{18}$$

The physical quantities of interest like Skin-friction coefficient (Cf), local Nusselt number (Nu) and local Sherwood number (Sh) are defined as

$$Cf = C_f(\sqrt{Re_x}) = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho u_w^2} = \sqrt{\frac{n+1}{2}} \left\{ (1+\beta) f'(0) - \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{n+1}{2} \right) \beta \lambda f''^3(0) \right\} \quad (19)$$

$$Nu = \frac{xq_w}{\kappa(T_f - T_\infty)} = -\frac{x \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}}{\kappa(T_f - T_\infty)} \Rightarrow Nu = -\sqrt{\frac{n+1}{2}} \left(1 + \frac{4R}{3} \right) (\sqrt{Re_x}) \theta'(0) \quad (20)$$

$$Sh_x = \frac{xq_m}{D_B(C_f - C_\infty)} = -\frac{D_B \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}}{(C_f - C_\infty)} \Rightarrow Sh = Sh_x(Re_x)^{\frac{-1}{2}} = -\sqrt{\frac{n+1}{2}} \phi'(0) \quad (21)$$

Numerical Method:

The present problem is solved by using finite element method, and is particularly efficient for solving differential equations, including partial and ordinary differential equations. As previously stated, the finite element technique is founded on the assumption that the domain may be divided into smaller, finite-dimensional entities called as finite elements. As of the time of writing, this is the most adaptable numerical technique to engineering analysis. Heat transfer, fluid mechanics, rigid body dynamics, solid mechanics, chemical processes, electrical systems, and acoustics are only a few of the phenomena studied using it. The finite element method is applied. Before doing a finite element analysis, the following must be completed:

- **Domain discretization into elements:** The whole interval is split into a limited number of subintervals known as elements using finite element discretization.
- **Domain decomposition into elements:** All of the previously listed elements are present in the finite-element mesh.
- **Use the method described below to create element equations:**
 1. The mathematical model is first modified to fit the typical element (a single mesh element).
 2. The element equations are created by substituting the estimated solution into the previously formed system, which is then solved for the variable, where there is an approximate solution to the variational issue.
 3. It is termed the rigidity matrix because it is created by interpolating polynomials.
- **Putting together and solving equations:** Every algebraic equation must be constructed using the inter-element continuity criteria. One can construct a global finite-element model of the entire domain by combining a lot of algebraic equations.
- **Imposition of boundary conditions:** The built-in equations must be subjected to the flow model's boundary conditions.

To solve constructed equations, a variety of numerical methods such as the LU decomposition method, the Gauss elimination method, and others can be utilised. When working with real numbers, it is critical to remember the form functions that are used to approximate real functions. The flow domain comprises a total of 20,001 nodes and is partitioned into 10,000 identical quadratic components. The flow domain is made up of 10,000 identical quadratic components. After developing the element equations, we were given 80,043 nonlinear equations to examine. Once the boundary conditions have been applied, the remaining system of nonlinear equations is numerically solved with an accuracy of 0.00001 using the Gauss elimination method. The use of Gaussian quadrature simplifies the problem. The MATHEMATICA programming language was used to write the method's desktop computer code.

3 Results and discussion

Program Code Validation:

The comparison of present Skin-friction coefficient ($-f''(0)$) results with the Skin-friction coefficient results of Cortell⁽³⁶⁾ in absence of first and second order slips, Porous medium, Powell-Eyring fluid, Casson fluid and Magnetic field effects is presented in Table 1. From this table, the comparison exposes that the present numerical results are congruent with the published results.

Table 1. Comparison of Skin-friction coefficient results with published results of Cortell⁽³⁶⁾ When $M \rightarrow 0, \beta \rightarrow 0, \lambda \rightarrow 0, K \rightarrow 0, \vartheta \rightarrow 0, \omega \rightarrow 0$ and $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$.

n	Cortell ⁽³⁶⁾	Present results
0.00	0.627547	0.606786437164037
0.20	0.766758	0.599439104079479
0.50	0.889477	0.870154782759862
0.75	0.953786	0.943567843056404
1.00	1.000000	0.986138658659781
1.5	1.061587	1.058738634760739

In the results and discussion section, the attained numerical solutions of velocity, temperature and concentration profiles are discussed using graphs for variations of different physical parameters such as Magnetic field parameter (M), Permeability parameter (K), Powell-Eyring fluid parameters (λ & β), Stretching sheet parameter (n), Prandtl number (Pr), Thermal radiation parameter (R), Thermophoresis parameter (Nt), Brownian motion parameter (Nb), First order velocity slip parameter (ϑ), Second order velocity slip parameter (ω), Thermal Biot number (δ), Mass Biot number (ζ), Casson fluid parameter (γ) and Lewis number (Le) in Figures 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 and followed by the calculated numerical values of engineering quantities such as Skin-friction coefficient (Cf), Rate of heat transfer coefficient in terms of Nusselt number (Nu) and Rate of mass transfer coefficient in terms of Sherwood number (Sh) are discussed and presented in Tables 2, 3 and 4. For entire graphs and tabular values, the basic values $M = 0.3, K = 0.5, \beta = 0.3, \lambda = 0.3, n = 0.3, Pr = 0.71, R = 0.5, Nb = 0.5, Nt = 0.3, \vartheta = 0.1, \omega = 0.1, Le = 0.3, \delta = 0.5, \gamma = 0.5$ and $\zeta = 0.5$ are fixed.

Figure 2 demonstrates the variations of Magnetic field parameter ($M \in [0.3, 1.0]$) on velocity profiles. As M elevates, a resistive force similar to a drag force is generated, which is known as Lorentz force. The velocity intensity is retarded by the Lorentz force, which decelerates its motion. Figure 3 explores fluid variable $\beta \in [0.3, 1.0]$ impact on velocity profiles. One can see that velocity and layer thickness are enhanced via larger β . Physically it can be observed that for higher values of β , the viscosity decreases due to which fluid velocity are enhanced. The effect of Casson fluid parameter ($\gamma \in [0.5, 2.0]$) on the fluid velocity is shown in Figure 8. Based on Figure 4, as γ increases, the fluid velocity decreases insignificantly. This means as the fluid behaves more like Newtonian fluid (as $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$), the thermal boundary layer becomes thicker and produce a lower rate of the heat dissipation in the system. It can be concluded that the fluid that behaves like Casson behaviour has a higher heat dissipation than Newtonian-like fluid. Figure 5 illustrates how the velocity profile was impacted by the first order slip parameter ($\vartheta \in [0.1, 1.0]$). With rising ϑ values, it has been demonstrated that the dimensionless velocity profile increases. As the velocity slip parameter rises, the slip velocity rises while the fluid velocity rises. This is because when the slip condition occurs, the stretched surface’s velocity is different from the flow velocity nearby. Figure 6 recognizes the effect of the Second order velocity slip parameter ($\omega \in [0.1, 1.0]$) on the velocity profiles. Due to the increasing nature of ω the result is not very impressive. As a result, the thickness of the hydrodynamic boundary layer is reduced, and the local velocity is reduced. The physical meaning of it is that when surface slip is present, it causes more slip at the surface, which results in less stretching sheet penetration into the fluid. Physically, the second-order slip parameter ω makes fluid motion more difficult, resulting in a thinner fluid flow field and the momentum barrier layer. Figures 7 and 8 depict, respectively, the effect of the Brownian motion parameter ($Nb \in [0.5, 1.5]$) on the temperature (θ) and concentration (ϕ) profiles. Temperature profiles rise as Brownian motion parameter values increase, but concentration profiles experience the opposite trend. The thickness of the boundary layer is proportional to the temperature of the nanofluid as a function of Nb. Figure 9 is drawn to depict the influence of Thermophoresis parameter ($Nt \in [0.3, 1.0]$), on temperature field. Larger values of thermophoresis parameter Nt constitutes a higher temperature field and thermal layer thickness. The reason behind this argument is that an enhancement in Nt yields a stronger thermophoretic force which allows deeper migration of nanoparticles in the fluid which is far away from the surface forms a higher temperature field and thickness of thermal layer. Fig. 10 shows that the higher thermophoresis parameter ($Nt \in [0.3, 1.0]$), yield a stronger concentration field.

Table 2 shows the numerical values of Skin-friction coefficient for variations in values of the engineering parameters such as, Magnetic field parameter ($M \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Permeability parameter ($K \in [0.5, 1.5]$), Powell-Eyring fluid parameters (λ & $\beta \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Stretching sheet parameter ($n \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Prandtl number ($Pr \in [0.71, 7.0]$), Thermal radiation parameter ($R \in [0.5, 2.0]$), Thermophoresis parameter ($Nt \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Brownian motion parameter ($Nb \in [0.5, 1.5]$), First order velocity slip parameter ($\vartheta \in [0.1, 1.0]$), Second order velocity slip parameter ($\omega \in [0.1, 1.0]$), Thermal Biot number ($\delta \in [0.5, 2.0]$), Mass Biot number ($\zeta \in [0.5, 2.0]$), Casson fluid parameter ($\gamma \in [0.5, 2.0]$) and Lewis number ($Le \in [0.5, 1.8]$). From this table, it is observed that the Skin-friction coefficient is increasing with rising values of Powell-Eyring fluid parameters ($\beta \in [0.3, 1.0]$),

Fig 2. Velocity profiles for variations of M

Fig 3. Velocity profiles for variations of β

Fig 4. Velocity profiles for variations of γ

Fig 5. Velocity profiles for variations of θ

Fig 6. Velocity profiles for variations of ω

Fig 7. Temperature profiles for variations of Nb

Fig 8. Concentration profiles for variations of Nb

Fig 9. Temperature profiles for variations of Nt

Fig 10. Concentration profiles for variations of Nt

Thermal radiation parameter ($R \in [0.5, 2.0]$), Thermophoresis parameter ($Nt \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Brownian motion parameter ($Nb \in [0.5, 1.5]$), Thermal Biot number ($\delta \in [0.5, 2.0]$), Mass Biot number ($\zeta \in [0.5, 2.0]$), while it is decreasing with increasing values of Magnetic field parameter ($M \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Permeability parameter ($K \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Powell-Eyring fluid parameter ($\lambda \in [0.3, 1.0]$), First order velocity slip parameter ($\vartheta \in [0.1, 1.0]$), Second order velocity slip parameter ($\omega \in [0.1, 1.0]$), Stretching sheet parameter ($n \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Prandtl number ($Pr \in [0.71, 7.0]$), Casson fluid parameter ($\gamma \in [0.5, 2.0]$) and Lewis number ($Le \in [0.5, 1.8]$). The numerical values of Nusselt number or rate of heat transfer coefficient are displayed in Table-3 for different values of Prandtl number ($Pr \in [0.71, 7.0]$), Thermal radiation parameter ($R \in [0.5, 2.0]$), Thermophoresis parameter ($Nt \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Brownian motion parameter ($Nb \in [0.5, 1.5]$), and Thermal Biot number ($\delta \in [0.5, 2.0]$). From this table, it is monitored that the rate of heat transfer coefficient is gradually rising with increasing values of Thermal radiation parameter ($R \in [0.5, 2.0]$), Thermophoresis parameter ($Nt \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Brownian motion parameter ($Nb \in [0.5, 1.5]$), and Thermal Biot number ($\delta \in [0.5, 2.0]$), while the overturn effect is observed in increasing values of Prandtl Number ($Pr \in [0.71, 7.0]$). The joint effects of Thermophoresis parameter ($Nt \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Brownian motion parameter ($Nb \in [0.5, 1.5]$), Mass Biot number ($\zeta \in [0.5, 2.0]$) and Lewis number ($Le \in [0.5, 1.8]$) on rate of mass transfer coefficient are discussed in Table-4. From this table, it is viewed that the rate of mass transfer coefficient is growing with increasing values of Thermophoresis parameter ($Nt \in [0.3, 1.0]$), Mass Biot number ($\zeta \in [0.5, 2.0]$) and declining with rising values of Brownian motion parameter ($Nb \in [0.5, 1.5]$), and Lewis number ($Le \in [0.5, 1.8]$).

Table 2. Numerical values of Skin-friction coefficient

M	β	K	λ	n	Pr	Nb	Nt	γ	ϑ	δ	ζ	Le	R	ω	Cf
0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.71	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	1.753983496838374
															1.726589679894546
															1.701452366983458
	0.6														1.787887871568782
	0.8														1.807890809834167
		1.0													1.736787535834539
		1.5													1.717976761736970
			0.6												1.717879680987317
			0.9												1.692645986769689
				0.5											1.777980978094578
				0.8											1.797870897891349
					1.00										1.711455876580766
					3.00										1.697631763407339
						0.8									1.786798769839812
						1.2									1.800986872348985
							0.5								1.796899867583919
							0.8								1.811892580767097
								1.0							1.727658267209341
								1.5							1.700987998139393
									0.5						1.779096136678907
									0.7						1.734678634198183
										1.0					1.760987879176060
										1.5					1.781326462380348
											1.0				1.789887316544581
											1.5				1.799962376734245
												1.0			1.730987349394693
												1.5			1.710987134767347
													1.0		1.788465286589374
													1.5		1.801456785608416
														0.5	1.725693614093469
														0.8	1.700984639736988

Table 3. Numerical values of rate of heat transfer coefficient

Pr	Nb	Nt	δ	R	Nu
0.71	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.655679836989374
1.00					0.616589798137669
3.00					0.599873673476309
	0.8				0.671478508748147
	1.2				0.690897873146906
		0.5			0.680985793769633
		0.8			0.708776745769361
			1.0		0.673467648756839
			1.5		0.693478704356807
				1.0	0.686733407763409
				1.5	0.706879857347494

Table 4. Numerical values of rate of mass transfer coefficient

Nb	Nt	ζ	Le	Sh
0.5	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.906819836793409
0.8				0.865697136903690
1.2				0.840987134989384
	0.5			0.946897319486745
	0.8			0.969873476976334
		1.0		0.937687368768098
		1.5		0.950987134597676
			1.0	0.878761358768054
			1.5	0.854356578734879

4 Conclusions

In the current examination, the joint effects of Thermophoresis and Brownian motion on MHD Powell-Eyring nanofluid over a stretched sheet filled by porous medium in the presence of Casson fluid flow particles, thermal and mass convective boundary conditions, first order and second order slip effects. The basic flow model equations’ similarity solution is obtained using the finite element technique. The key findings of this investigation are as follows:

- The velocity profiles and momentum boundary thickness decrease with the fluid parameters $M, K, \vartheta, \gamma, \omega$ and λ , while increase with n and β .
- Temperature profiles are improved with increasing R, Nb, Nt, δ , and falls with rising values of Pr .
- The concentration profiles and the boundary layer both demonstrate a decline in concentration with Nb, Le and increase with Nt , and ζ .
- Finally, the gained mathematical results are more accurate through the published results of Cortell⁽¹⁵⁾ in a limiting case by taking $M \rightarrow 0, \beta \rightarrow 0, \lambda \rightarrow 0, K \rightarrow 0, \vartheta \rightarrow 0, \omega \rightarrow 0$ and $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$.

The results of this study show that increasing the value of the fluid parameter causes the fluid to accelerate more quickly and that the fluid’s random motion enables it to produce more heat, which can be employed in industrial settings. Future studies will focus on the dynamics of heat transfer in hybrid nanofluids with convective boundary conditions, using Powell-Eyring type fluid as the base fluid and analysing how other non-Newtonian fluid types (like Casson, Ferro, Oldroyd B-fluid, Williamson fluids, and so on) behave under analogous conditions. The Powell-Eyring fluid will serve as the foundation fluid for this project.

5 Nomenclature

List of Symbols:

u, v : x and y directions velocity components respectively (m/s)
 x, y : Cartesian coordinates calculated along the stretching sheet (m)
 f : Dimensionless stream function
 f' : Fluid velocity (m/s)
 Pr : Prandtl number
 T : Fluid temperature (K)
 B_0 : Uniform magnetic field (Tesla)
 M : Magnetic field parameter
 u_w : Stretching velocity of the fluid (m/s)
 C : Fluid nanoparticle volume concentration (mol / m³)
 C_∞ : Dimensional ambient volume fraction (mol / m³)
 C_f : Dimensional concentration of hot fluid (mol / m³)
 T_f : Dimensional temperature of hot fluid
 T_∞ : Temperature of the fluid far-off from the stretching sheet (K)
 Cf : Skin-friction coefficient (s⁻¹)
 Nu : Rate of heat transfer coefficient (or) Nusselt number
 Nb : Brownian motion parameter
 Nt : Thermophoresis parameter
 C^* : Material constant
 Le : Lewis number
 q_w : Heat flux coefficient
 q_m : Mass flux coefficient
 C_p : Nano particles Specific heat capacity (J / kg / K)
 D_B : Coefficient of Brownian diffusion
 D_T : Coefficient of Thermophoresis diffusion (m² / s)
 Sh : Rate of mass transfer coefficient (or) Sherwood number
 K : Permeability parameter (m⁻¹)
 k_1 : Permeability of porous medium (m⁻¹)
 a : Positive real number
 Re_∞ : Reynold's number
 T_m : Fluid Mean temperature
 R : Thermal radiation parameter
 q_r : Radiative heat flux
 K^* : Mean absorption coefficient
 n : Stretching sheet parameter

Greek symbols

η : Dimensionless similarity variable (m)
 θ : Non-dimensional temperature (K)
 ϕ : Non-Dimensional nanoparticle concentration (mol / m³)
 α_m : Thermal diffusivity, (m² / s)
 ν : Kinematic viscosity, (m² / s)
 σ : Electrical conductivity
 ρ_f : Fluid density, (kg / m³)
 μ : Dynamic viscosity of the fluid,
 κ : Thermal conductivity of the fluid, (W / (m·K))
 τ_w : Shear stress
 δ : Thermal Biot number
 ζ : Mass Biot number
 β_1 : Non-uniform heat transfer coefficient
 λ_1 : Non-uniform mass transfer coefficient
 σ^* : Stefan Boltzmann constant
 β : Powell-Eyring fluid parameter
 λ : Powell-Eyring fluid parameter

χ : Material constant
 ϑ : First order velocity slip parameter
 ω : Second order velocity slip parameter

Superscript:

/: Differentiation w.r.t η

Subscripts:

f : Fluid,
 w : Condition on the sheet,
 ∞ : Ambient Conditions.

References

- Choi SUS. Enhancing thermal conductivity of fluids with nanoparticles. vol. 66. USA, ASME, FED 231/MD. 1995;p. 99–105. Available from: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/196525>.
- Hayat JB, Awais T, Asghar M, S. Radiative effects in a three-dimensional flow of MHD Eyring-Powell fluid. *J Egypt Math Soc.* 2006;128(3):379–384. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joems.2013.02.009>.
- Hayat T, Iqbal Z, Qasim M, Obaidat S. Steady flow of an Eyring Powell fluid over a moving surface with convective boundary conditions. *Int J Heat Mass Transfer.* 2012;55(7-8):1817–1822. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2011.10.046>.
- Hayat T, Asad S, Mustafa M, Alsaedi A. Radiation effects on the flow of Powell-Eyring fluid past an unsteady inclined stretching sheet with non-uniform heat source/sink. *Article e103214.* 2014;9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0103214>.
- Bhatti MM, Abbas T, Rashidi MM, Ali ME, Yang S, Z. Entropy generation on MHD Eyring-Powell nanofluid through a permeable stretching surface. *Entropy.* 2016;18(6):224–224. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/e18060224>.
- Khan I, Qasim M, Shafie S. Flow of an Eyring-Powell fluid over a stretching sheet in presence of chemical reaction. *Therm Sci.* 2016;20(6):1903–1912. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijcre-2014-0090>.
- Halim A, Noor NM, F N. Mixed convection flow of Powell-Eyring nanofluid near a stagnation point along a vertical stretching sheet. *Mathematics.* 2021;9(4):364–364. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9040364>.
- Jamshed W, Eid MR, Nisar KS, Nasir NAAM, Edacherian A, Saleel CA, et al. A numerical frame work of magnetically driven Powell-Eyring nanofluid using single phase model. *Sci Rep.* 2021;11(1):1–26. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-96040-0>.
- Mostafa A, Abdelhafez AA, Awad MA, Nafe DA, Eisa. Flow of mixed convection for radiative and magnetic hybrid nanofluid in a porous material with Joule heating. *Heat Transfer.* 2022;4:2995–3017. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/htj.22433>.
- Malik M, Khan I, Hussain A, Salahuddin T. Mixed convection flow of MHD Eyring-Powell nanofluid over a stretching sheet: A numerical study. *Article 117118.* 2015;5. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4935639>.
- Ahmed M, Mohamed AR, Dalia AN, Eisa2. Heat Generation and Thermal Radiation Impacts on Flow of Magnetic Eyring-Powell Hybrid Nanofluid in a Porous Medium. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering.* 2023;48:939–952. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-022-07210-9>.
- Rashad AM, Nafe MA, Daliaa, Eisa. Heat variation on MHD Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow with convective boundary condition and Ohmic heating in a porous material. *Scientific Reports.* 2023;13:6071–6071. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-33043-z>.
- Mohamed R. Thermal conductivity variation and heat generation effects on magneto-hybrid nanofluid flow in a porous medium with slip condition. *Waves in Random and Complex Media* ;32:1103–1127. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17455030.2020.1810365>.
- Agrawal R, Kaswan P, Eyring M. Powell nanofluid past over an unsteady exponentially stretching surface with entropy generation and thermal radiation. *Heat Transfer.* 2021;50(5):4669–4693. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/htj.22095>.
- Abdelhafez MA, Awad MA, Nafe DA, Eisa. Effects of yield stress and chemical reaction on magnetic two-phase nanofluid flow in a porous regime with thermal ray. *Indian J Phys.* 2022;96(12):3579–3589. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12648-022-02288-1>.
- Ahmed M, Mohamed AR, Dalia AN, Eisa2. Heat Generation and Thermal Radiation Impacts on Flow of Magnetic Eyring-Powell Hybrid Nanofluid in a Porous Medium. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering.* 2023;48:939–952. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/htj.22433>.
- Rashad AM, Nafe MA, Daliaa, Eisa. Heat variation on MHD Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow with convective boundary condition and Ohmic heating in a porous material. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering.* 2023;13:6071–6071. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-33043-z>.
- Mohamed R. Thermal conductivity variation and heat generation effects on magneto-hybrid nanofluid flow in a porous medium with slip condition. *Scientific Reports*;32:1103–1127. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17455030.2020.1810365>.
- Qayyum S, Hayat T, Shehzad SA, Alsaedi A. Nonlinear convective flow of Powell-Eyring magneto nanofluid with Newtonian heating. *Results Phys.* 2017;7:2933–2940. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17455030.2020.1810365>.
- Qayyum S, Hayat T, Shehzad SA, Alsaedi A. Nonlinear convective flow of Powell-Eyring magneto nanofluid with Newtonian heating. *Results in Physics.* 2017;7:2933–2940. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2017.08.001>.
- Akbar NS, Ebaid A, Khan ZH. Numerical analysis of magnetic field effects on Eyring-Powell fluid flow towards a stretching sheet. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials.* 2015;382:355–358. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2015.01.088>.
- Gireesha BJ, Gorla RSR, Mahanthesh B. Effect of Suspended Nanoparticles on Three-Dimensional MHD Flow, Heat and Mass Transfer of Radiating Eyring-Powell Fluid Over a Stretching Sheet. *Journal of Nanofluids.* 2015;4(4):474–484. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1166/jon.2015.1177>.
- Roşca AV, Pop I. Flow and heat transfer of Powell-Eyring fluid over a shrinking surface in a parallel free stream. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer.* 2014;71:321–327. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2013.12.020>.
- Nadeem S, Mushtaq A, Alzabut J, Ghazwani HA, Eldin SM. The flow of an Eyring Powell Nanofluid in a porous peristaltic channel through a porous medium. *Scientific Reports.* 2023;13(1):9694–9694. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-36136-x>.
- Al-Mamun A, Arifuzzaman SM, Reza-E-Rabbi S, Alam US, Islam S, Khan MS. Numerical simulation of periodic MHD Casson nanofluid flow through porous stretching sheet. *SN Applied Sciences.* 2021;3(2):271–271. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s42452-021-04140-3>.
- Abdelhafez MA, Awad AA, Nafe MA, Eisa DA. Time-dependent viscous flow of higher-order reactive MHD Maxwell nanofluid with Joule heating in a porous regime. *Waves in Random and Complex Media.* 2024;34(3):1041–1061. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17455030.2021.1927237>.

- 27) Kumar YS, Hussain S, Raghunath K, Ali F, Guedri K, Eldin SM, et al. Numerical analysis of magnetohydrodynamics Casson nanofluid flow with activation energy, Hall current and thermal radiation. *Scientific Reports*. 2023;13(1):4021–4021. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-28379-5>.
- 28) Rikitu EH. Flow Dynamics of Eyring–Powell Nanofluid on Porous Stretching Cylinder under Magnetic Field and Viscous Dissipation Effects. *Advances in Mathematical Physics*. 2023;2023:1–18. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2023/9996048>.
- 29) Abbas W, Megahed AM, Emam MS, Sadek HMH. MHD dissipative Powell-Eyring fluid flow due to a stretching sheet with convective boundary conditions and slip velocity. *Scientific Reports*. 2023;13(1):15674–15674. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-42609-w>.
- 30) Meenakumari R, Lakshminarayana P. MHD 3D flow of powell eyring fluid over a bidirectional non-linear stretching surface with temperature dependent conductivity and heat absorption/generation. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part E: Journal of Process Mechanical Engineering*. 2022;236(6):2580–2588. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/09544089221097695>.
- 31) Rashad A, Nafe M, Eisa D. 2D Radiative Casson-Carreau Hybrid Nanofluid Flow through a Circular Cylinder in a Darcy-Forchheimer Porous Medium. Egypt's Presidential Specialized Council for Education and Scientific Research. 2023. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.21608/nujbas.2023.218751.1012>.
- 32) Rashad AM, Nafe MA, Eisa DA. Yield Stress Impact on Magnetohydrodynamic Jeffery Hybrid Nanofluid Flow Over a Moving Porous Surface: Buongiorno's Model. *Results Phys*. 2023;12:1729–1738. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1166/jon.2023.2057>.
- 33) Rashad AM, Nafe MA, Eisa DA. Variation of thermal conductivity and heat on magnetic maxwell hybrid nanofluid viscous flow in a porous system with higher-order chemical react. 2023;14:17–32. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1615/SpecialTopicsRevPorousMedia.2023045731>.
- 34) Mustafa M, Khan JA, Hayat T, Alsaedi A. Boundary layer flow of nanofluid over a nonlinearly stretching sheet with convective boundary condition. *IEEE Trans Nanotech*. 2015;14:159–168. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijthermalsci.2011.02.019>.
- 35) Hayat T, Sajjad R, Muhammad T, Alsaedi A, Ellahi R. On MHD nonlinear stretching flow of powell-eyring nanomaterial. *Results in Physics*. 2017;7:535–543. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2016.12.039>.
- 36) R. Viscous flow and heat transfer over a nonlinearly stretching sheet. *Appl Math Comput*. 2007;184:864–873. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1615/SpecialTopicsRevPorousMedia.2023045731>.